

Wolff-Kishner Reduction Studies on Steroidal Hydrazone Oxime

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Wolff-Kishner reaction is a reliable method to convert a carbonyl function to methylene. But it is also well known that the hydrazones of α -oximinoketones when subjected to the normal reaction conditions of Wolff-Kishner reaction give triazoles¹. It was of interest to prepare steroidal triazoles using this convenient method. However, we found that steroidal hydrazone oxime when subjected to the normal conditions of Wolff-Kishner reaction, gave the usual product, which we report herein.

(25R)-4-Hydroxy-4-spirosten-3-one (**1**)² on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine at room temperature gave 3-oxime (**2**). Appearance of pink-violet colour with ferric chloride³ indicated the presence of free enolic hydroxyl group, while green precipitates with copper acetate⁴ indicated the presence of *anti*-form of oxime function. Uv

spectrum showed a bathochromic shift from 257 to 289 nm in alkaline methanol. The hydrazone (**3**) was prepared by treating steroidal oxime (**2**) with hydrazine hydrate in refluxing ethanol. It exhibited the $\lambda_{\max}$ at 276 and 349 nm and nmr signals at δ 0.66 (3H, s, 19-CH₃) and 0.72 (3H, s, 18-CH₃). The hydrazone oxime (**3**) on treatment with KOH in ethylene glycol afforded a product, which was identified as (25R)-3-oximino-5 α -spirostane. It showed 19- and 18-methyl signals at δ 0.84 and 0.74 respectively. Assignment of α -configuration at C-5 is in accordance with the earlier reports⁵.

Experimental

M.p.s. reported are uncorrected. Pmr spectra (CDCl₃; 60/90 MHz) were recorded using TMS as internal reference, ir spectra were recorded in KBr and electronic spectra in methanol. Elemental analyses data of all the compounds were found satisfactory. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

(25R)-4-Hydroxy-3-oximino-4-spirosten-3-one (**2**) : To a stirred solution of (25R)-4-hydroxy-4-spirosten-3-one (**1**; 1 g) in pyridine (15 ml) was added hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.2 g) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h and then poured in ice-cold water (500 ml). The resulting white solid was washed, dried and crystallised from methanol (0.52 g), m.p. 232–34^od (Found : C, 72.7; H, 9.4; N, 2.9. C₂₇H₄₁NO₄ requires : C, 73.1; H, 9.3; N, 3.2%);

$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) 257 (4.09) and 289 (4.11), $\nu_{\max}$ 3425, 1670 and 1454 cm^{-1} , δ 0.83 (3H, s), 1.06 (3H, s), 3.41 (2H, m) and 4.43 (1H, m)

(25R)-3-Oximino-5 α -spirosten-4-one hydrazone (3)

To a solution of (25R)-4-hydroxy-3-oximino-4-spirostene (2, 1 g) in ethanol (120 ml) were added a few drops of glacial acetic acid and hydrazine hydrate (1 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 1 h, then concentrated to 30 ml and allowed to stand for crystallisation. The crystals were filtered, washed, and dried (0.65 g), mp 194–96° (Found C, 70.7, H, 9.4, N, 9.0 $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{43}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.9, H, 9.5, N, 9.2%), $\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) 276 (3.65) and 349 (3.36), $\nu_{\max}$ 3365, 1450 and 1381 cm^{-1} , δ 0.66 (3H, s), 0.72 (3H, s), 3.39 (2H, m) and 4.39 (1H, m)

(25R)-3-Oximino-5 α -spirostene (4) A mixture of (25R)-3-oximino-5 α -spirosten-4-one hydrazone (3, 1 g), KOH (0.5 g), and ethylene glycol (25 ml) was refluxed for 45 min. The mixture was then cooled, poured in ice-cold water and the aqueous suspension was extracted with chloroform (3 $\times$ 100 ml). The combined chloroform extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent recovered under reduced pressure to give

a brown solid which was crystallised from methanol, (0.5 g), mp 254–56° (Found N, 3.7 $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{43}\text{NO}_3$ requires N, 3.3%), $\nu_{\max}$ 3294, 1451 and 1381 cm^{-1} , δ 0.72 (3H, s), 0.84 (3H, s), 3.42 (2H, m) and 4.38 (1H, m)

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